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Assessment Of Data Protection And Privacy Implementation In Financial Institutions In Nigeria

Umar Nuruddeen; Gilbert I. O. Aimufua; Bilkisu Maijamaa & Steven Bassey

**Centre for Cyberspace Studies
Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria
umarnuruddeen002@gmail.com**

ABSTRACT

The study investigated data protection and privacy implementation in financial institutions in Nigeria. The study was guided by four objectives. Quantitative research methodology was adopted for the study through a correlational research design. The theories underpinned the study were Institutional Theory, Information Privacy Theory and Regulatory Compliance Theory. The population of the study consisted of five financial institutions in Nigeria that handle personal and sensitive data total 108. Purposive sampling was used to select respondent knowledgeable in data protection and privacy practices within the financial institutions in Nigeria. The data was collected using questionnaire. The data was collected online using Google forms. The data was analysed using descriptive statistics and the hypotheses were tested using inferential statistical (Person Product Moment Correlation). The findings revealed effectiveness of the existing regulatory environment, effectiveness and strong compliance with data protection standards. Further, there was a positive correlation between data protection, privacy implementation, regulatory environment with data compliance with the significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). The study concluded that financial institution studied adheres to data protection and privacy compliance and recommended that financial institutions should establish dedicated compliance units that conduct periodic internal audits to assess adherence to data protection policies, they should adopt international best practices, such as ISO 27701 (Privacy Information Management System) and GDPR guidelines, to maintain global competitiveness and they should continuously update on their privacy policies in line with emerging cybersecurity threats and technological. Additionally, financial institutions should be required to conduct mandatory cybersecurity resilience assessments and submit periodic compliance reports to regulatory authorities.

Keywords: Data compliance, data protection, financial institutions, regulatory environment

INTRODUCTION

In the present age, data protection and privacy is gaining attention as a result of the important of data in the global community. Today, the world has become a global village as a result of the internet that connects people for information exchange. Most of the world's firms have shifted to carrying out their operations digitally, leading the continuous flow of personal data (Bejide, 2021).

Added to the above, and most importantly, constant breaches of sensitive data around the world have become a concern for individuals and organisations. Many organisations such as Facebook and Uber have been cyber-attack victims. For example, in September 2018, Uber reported a cyber-attack on its data. This affected over 57 million drivers and customers. Further, Facebook had the same experience in

September 2018, where 90 million accounts of users were breached in the United Kingdom (Techworld Staff, 2018). Recently, the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) ascertained and informed the public that the Lagos State Internal Revenue Service (LIRS) published a site <https://lagos.qpay.ng/TaxPayer> where personal information of tax payers of Lagos State was gleaned by the general public in breach of the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation Act (NDPR), 2019.

With these cyber-attacks and breaches, many countries globally and firms have not taken data privacy as their focus, especially the third world countries like Nigeria. Further, our lives are now more digitized to the online space. With this, the issue of data protection is now becoming more difficult than before. Social pressure, new technologies and cultural trends push us to sharing our personal data with others. People on the social network have interest in these data, as well as government and organisations. Also, most of the data this the world produced are data that are personal and can be traced back to particular people (Scott & Eke, 2020).

Traditionally, firms use diverse methods of de-identification such as anonymization, pseudonymization, encryption, key-coding, and data sharing to distance data from their real identities and permit analysis to continue while at the same time dealing with privacy issues. Over the years, computer scientists have stated that even anonymized data can also be re-identified and attributed to particular people (Suleiman & Danjuma, 2022). The last decades have witness the introduction and fortifying of laws for data protection in some nations (Syafitri, et al, 2022). For example in Europe, General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is now used in place of Data Protection Directive (Directive 95/46/EC) since May, 2018.

In the context of Nigeria, the legal and regulatory laws guiding data protection has under gone changes in recent years. Nigeria Data Protection Act (NDPA) introduction in 2023 was a significant step in solving data privacy challenges in the country. The NDPA, which was enacted by the National Assembly of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, states procedures for personal data collection, processing and management, imposing a duty on firms to make sure of security of data and protection of the privacy rights of individuals. It as well serves as a legal law for the protection of personal information and set up the Nigeria Data Protection Commission responsible for controlling of personal information procession (NDPA, 2023). The regulation is impacted by world best practices, specifically the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), that is used as the yardstick for data protection standards globally (GDPR, 2018).

Regulatory compliance plays an important part in shaping the operation of firms and business around the world. In Nigeria, a country with different and dynamic economic system, regulatory compliance is of most significance. It makes sure of stability and integrity of different organization and aid trust and confidence among stakeholders. In as much as there is establishment of regulatory laws, issues still continue in attaining complete compliance with standards of data protection. Challenges such as lack of awareness, inadequate training, infrastructure and constraints of resources hindered the effectiveness of data protection implementation in Nigerian financial institutions (Bejide, 2021). Also, the diverse nature of cyber-attack needs constant updates and improvements to methods of data protection to mitigate these risks.

Financial institutions in Nigeria, serves as keepers of personal and financial information that is sensitive, thus, they need to stick to regulations of data protection and privacy to make sure of the security and confidentiality of data of customers. These institutions play an important part in different financial services, such as saving, investment, loans, and credit facilities, all deals with handling large volumes of financial and personal data. Thus, compliance with the regulations of data protection is necessary not because it is a legal duty but for keeping operational integrity and enhancing trust of customers (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2024).

Statement of the problem

Nigeria's financial institutions sectors, as observed have an issue with data privacy, needing immediate attention and careful exploration. The present situation shows a gap between the real condition of data protection and the realities of the digital environment. This gap is an issue that requires further research, prompting the current study.

This gap is as a result of lack of awareness creation and data privacy laws and regulations implementation in Nigeria's financial institutions sector. The lack of awareness among the data privacy right of the public has brought about privacy infractions. Also, lack of legal precedents as well as resources serves as a barrier. This situation requires a thorough exploration to bridge the gap between the theoretical and practical implementation of data privacy regulations.

Thus, this study focus on addressing this research gap by exploration of data protection and privacy implementation in financial institutions in Nigeria, so as to know the areas for improvement, and give recommendations to improve the ability of banks to effectively protect customers data.

Research Questions

In addressing the above problem, this research aims to address the following research questions:

- i. What is the level of compliance with the Nigerian Data Protection Act 2023(NDPA) governing data privacy and protection in the financial institutions in Nigeria?
- ii. What is the effectiveness of existing data protection by the financial institutions in Nigeria?
- iii. What is the effectiveness of existing privacy implementation by the financial institutions in Nigeria?
- iv. What is the effectiveness of the existing regulatory environment of data protection and privacy compliance by the financial institutions in Nigeria?

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to assess data protection and privacy compliance in financial institutions in Nigeria. The specific objectives of this research study are to:

- i. Assess the level of compliance with the Nigerian Data Protection Act (NDPA) 2023 governing data privacy and protection in the financial institutions in Nigeria
- ii. Evaluate the effectiveness of existing data protection by the financial institutions.
- iii. Determine the effectiveness of existing privacy implementation by the financial institutions.
- iv. Investigate the effectiveness of the existing regulatory environment by the financial institutions

Hypotheses

The null hypotheses will be tested at a 0.05 level of significance

H01: There is no significant relationship between data protection and data compliance in financial institutions in Nigeria

H02: There is no significant relationship between privacy implementation and data compliance in financial institutions in Nigeria

H03: There is no significant relationship between the regulatory environment and data compliance in financial institutions in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Adebayo, and Adekunle (2023) explored data protection and compliance among financial institutions in Lagos state, Nigeria. The study employed a quantitative method with through a cross-sectional design. The study population was financial institutions with sample of 120 institutions. The results showed that the rates of compliance was low as result of limitations of resources and lack of knowledge of regulatory needs, with most of the institutions focusing on profitability more than ways to enhance data protection. The study was limited to Lagos financial institutions, narrowing the scope of the study which this study will cover.

Musa and Abubakar (2022) studies privacy practices in the banking sector in Nigeria. Mixed method was used by the study. Interviews and surveys were used with descriptive research design. The population of the study consisted of 15 commercial banks, making a sample size of 450. The result of the study showed a lack of privacy policies and compliance was strictly based on regulatory inspections but not based on the commitment of the institution to privacy protection.

Nwankwo and Eze (2023) examined the challenges and way forward for protection of data in the banking sector in Nigeria. The study used qualitative method. The population of the study was five banks and 30 participants were interviewed. The results indicated that challenges such as lack of staff training, lack of

awareness about regulation and data management infrastructures that were out of date, all preventing the effective practices of data protection.

Onu and Chukwu (2021) investigated the effect of regulatory policies on the data protection and compliance in financial institutions. Quantitative method and cross sectional survey design was used. The population was regulatory officers and compliance managers, totalling 200. The results revealed that in as much as regulatory policies impact data protection positively, a lot of institutions have challenges with implementation as a result of cost related to compliance.

Okoro and Amadi (2020) examined the challenges of data protection regulations implementation in banks in Nigeria. The study made use of a qualitative case study with population of 20 IT and compliance officers. The result of the study revealed lack of skilled personnel, inadequate budget and complexity in adapting world standards to the context of Nigeria were the hindrance for effective implementation of data protection.

METHODOLOGY

The research method used was a quantitative research methodology. The study adopted a correlation research design to explore data protection and privacy implementation within financial institutions in Nigeria. The study's population of 108 workers comprised of Information Technology Department, Legal and Compliance Department, Customer Service Department, Human Resources Department, and Risk Management Department of selected financial institutions under study. The study made use of a purposive sampling technique. The sampling techniques are suitable for the research because they allowed the selection of workers who have knowledge and are involved directly in data privacy and protection in the financial institutions in Nigeria. The data was collected through the use of a questionnaire. Specifically, the study made use of a structured questionnaire which was distributed to respondents across in financial institutions in Nigeria. Data from questionnaires was analyzed using correlation to quantify the extent of privacy, protection, and compliance related to data protection in financial institutions in Nigeria. The hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation. SPSS was used to facilitate this analysis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table I: Compliance with the Nigerian Data Protection Act

Items	VHL	HL	ML	LL	Mean	SD
The institution fully adheres to the requirements outlined in the Nigerian Data Protection Act 2023 (NDPA).	49(47.6%)	37(35.9%)	17(16.5%)	0	4.3	.7
There are established policies to ensure compliance with the NDPA in handling customer data.	49(47.6%)	43(41.7%)	11(10.7%)	0	4.1	.6
Employees are adequately trained on the NDPA regulations and their responsibilities regarding data privacy.	50(48.5%)	32(31.1%)	21(20.4%)	0	4.2	.8
This institution regularly audits its data protection practices to ensure NDPA compliance.	50(48.5%)	42(40.8%)	11(10.7%)	0	3.1	.6
Data collection and processing practices align with the consent and transparency requirements of the NDPA.	39(37.9%)	47(45.6%)	17(16.5%)	0	4.3	.7
Customer consent is obtained and recorded as required by the NDPA before processing personal data.	67(65%)	25(24.3%)	11(10.7%)	0	3.3	.6
Customers are informed of their rights under the NDPA regarding their personal data held by the institution.	56(54.4%)	19(18.4%)	28(27.2%)	0	4.2	.4
There are robust data protection mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorized access to customer information.	38(38.9%)	65(63.1%)	0	0	3.4	.5
The institution has a clear process for handling customer complaints related to data protection, in line with NDPA.	49(47.6%)	31(30.1%)	23(22.3%)	0	2.3	.8
Data retention and disposal practices comply with the guidelines specified by the NDPA.	44(42.7%)	48(46.6%)	11(10.7%)	0	4.2	.8
Regular reviews are conducted to ensure third-party vendors comply with NDPA standards when handling customer data.	45(43.7%)	41(39.8%)	17(16.5%)	0	4.3	.7
There is a dedicated Data Protection Officer (DPO) responsible for ensuring NDPA compliance within the institution.	45(43.7%)	43(41.7%)	15(14.6%)	0	3.0	.7
This institution regularly updates its privacy policy to reflect any changes in the NDPA.	56(54.4%)	41(39.8%)	6(5.8%)	0	4.4	.6
Grand mean					3.7	

The result from table 4.2 shows that financial institutions in Nigeria comply with the Nigerian Data Protection Act (NDPA) 2023. Constant update of privacy policies was rate highest with (Mean = 4.4, SD = 0.6) and data collection practices alignment with transparency and consent (Mean = 4.3, SD = 0.7). Added to the above, compliance with policies (Mean = 4.1, SD = 0.6) and workers training (Mean = 4.2, SD = 0.8) were rated positively. In the other hand, procedure for customer consent (Mean = 3.3, SD = 0.6) and review of third party compliance (Mean = 4.3, SD = 0.7), complaint handling process of institution (Mean = 2.3, SD = 0.8) and availability of data protection officer that are dedicated had (Mean = 3.0, SD = 0.7). The cumulative mean of 3.7 suggests high extent of compliance among financial institutions in Nigeria.

Table II: Effectiveness of existing data protection

Items	SA	A	UD	SD	Mean	SD
The data protection policies of this financial institution are effective in securing customer data.	59(57.3%)	44(42.7%)	0	0	4.3	.49
Data encryption protocols are robust enough to prevent unauthorized access.	53(51.5%)	50(48.5%)	0	0	3.2	.50
Employees receive adequate training on data protection practices and regulations.	53(51.5%)	50(48.5%)	0	0	4.2	.51
The institution uses advanced technology to prevent data breaches.	69(67%)	28(27.2%)	6(5.8%)	0	3.5	.53
Regular data security audits are conducted to identify vulnerabilities.	64(62.1%)	33(32%)	6(5.8%)	0	3.4	.57
This financial institution complies fully with national and international data protection standards.	53(51.5%)	50(48.5%)	0	0	4.4	.48
The institution's response to potential data breaches is timely and effective.	65(63.1%)	32(31.1%)	6(5.8%)		4.5	.56
Customer data is handled with strict confidentiality across all departments.	65(63.1%)	38(36.9%)	0	0	4.1	.43
Multi-factor authentication is effectively used to protect customer accounts.	47(45.6%)	56(54.4%)	0	0	3.6	.54
There is adequate monitoring in place to detect and prevent data breaches.	43(41.7%)	48(46.6%)	12(11.7%)	0	4.2	.57
Customers are informed promptly if there are any data protection concerns.	47(45.6%)	56(54.4%)	0	0	4.4	.50
The institution has a dedicated team for managing data privacy and security.	59(57.3%)	38(36.9%)	6(5.8%)		3.7	.61
Grand mean					3.9	

The result shows that financial institution shows effectiveness of data protection, specifically in making sure that customer data is secured (Mean = 4.3, SD = 0.49) and ensuring that across departments, there is strict confidentiality (Mean = 4.1, SD = 0.43). Workers are trained well in data protection practice (Mean = 4.2, SD = 0.51), and customers are well informed about data protection concerns (Mean = 4.4, SD = 0.50). Further, there is effective use of multi-factor authentication (Mean = 3.6, SD = 0.54) and used of advanced technology for breaches prevention (Mean = 3.5, SD = 0.53), improving of encryption protocols to make sure that are robust (Mean = 3.2, SD = 0.50) and improving measures of monitoring (Mean = 4.2, SD = 0.57). Added to the above, a dedicated data privacy team is available (Mean = 3.7, SD = 0.61), implying that inasmuch as efforts are put in place, enhancing the structure of security governance could improve the whole institution's data protection framework.

Table III: Effectiveness of Existing Privacy Implementation

Items	SA	A	UD	SD	Mean	STD
This financial institution has a clear and comprehensive privacy policy for protecting customer information.	59(57.3%)	44(42.7%)	0	0	4.7	.48
Privacy policies are regularly updated to align with current regulations and industry standards.	50(48.5%)	36(34.9%)	12(11.6%)	5(4.8%)	4.6	.56
Employees are well-informed and trained on the institution's privacy compliance policies.	53(51.5%)	33(32%)	17(16.5%)	0	3.6	.56
The institution effectively limits access to customer information based on roles and responsibilities.	69(67%)	28(27.2%)	6(5.8%)	0	4.4	.57
Privacy compliance is actively monitored to ensure adherence across all departments.	42(40.8%)	49(47.6%)	7(6.8%)	5(4.8%)	3.4	.48
This institution complies with all relevant national and international privacy regulations (e.g., GDPR).	64(62.1%)	30(29.1%)	4(3.8%)	5(4.8%)	4.6	.48
Customer consent is obtained before collecting, using, or sharing personal data.	47(45.6%)	37(35.9%)	10(9.7%)	9(8.7%)	4.5	.57
Customers are notified promptly about any changes to privacy policies.	60(58.3%)	31(30.1%)	8(7.8%)	4(3.8%)	3.5	.53
Privacy audits are conducted regularly to identify potential compliance issues.	35(33.9%)	38(36.9%)	16(15.5%)	14(13.6%)	4.6	.47
The institution has clear procedures for customers to access and manage their personal data.	49(47.6%)	40(38.8%)	7(6.8%)	7(6.8%)	4.3	.58
Privacy compliance measures protect customer data from unauthorized use or disclosure.	37(35.9%)	30(29.1%)	16(15.3%)	20(19.4%)		
There is a clear and accessible process for customers to file complaints regarding privacy concerns.	47(45.6%)	33(32%)	13(12.6%)	10(9.7%)	3.2	.56
Grand mean					4.1	

The results shows that financial institutions in Nigeria are well committed to protection of privacy as shown by it privacy policy (Mean = 4.7, SD = 0.48) and adherence to international and national privacy regulations (Mean = 4.6, SD = 0.48). Constant updates of privacy policies (Mean = 4.6, SD = 0.56) and enforcement of access control (Mean = 4.4, SD = 0.57) as well help to reinforcement of data security. Consent of customer practices (Mean = 4.5, SD = 0.57) and methods for the management of personal data (Mean = 4.3, SD = 0.58) were all put in place. This notwithstanding, monitoring of privacy compliance (Mean = 3.4, SD = 0.48) and handling of complain from customers (Mean = 3.2, SD = 0.56) need to be enhanced. Added to the above, in as much as privacy audits are done (Mean = 4.6, SD = 0.47), workers awareness and training on policies compliance (Mean = 3.6, SD = 0.56) may help to strengthened to make sure of compliance. The cumulative mean of 4.1 indicates the effectiveness to privacy protections of financial institutions in Nigeria.

Table IV: Effectiveness of the existing regulatory environment

Items	SA	A	DA	SD	Mean	STD
The regulatory framework in this institution effectively protects customer data from breaches.	61(59.2%)	30(29.1%)	8(7.8%)	5(4.8%)	4.1	.48
Compliance with regulatory standards is a top priority in this institution.	60(58.3%)	29(28.2%)	8(7.8%)	6(5.8%)	3.4	.47
This institution ensures all practices are aligned with current financial regulatory requirements.	55(53.4%)	34(33%)	9(8.7%)	5(4.8%)	3.1	.46
Regulatory guidelines are clearly communicated to employees.	45(43.7%)	40(38.8%)	11(10.7%)	7(6.8%)	3.5	.56
The institution actively reviews and updates policies to comply with changes in regulations.	62(60.2%)	31(30.1%)	10(9.7%)	0	4.7	.50
Regulatory compliance efforts are effectively monitored across all departments.	61(59.2%)	25(24.3%)	0	17(16.5%)	4.3	.47
There are sufficient resources allocated for ensuring regulatory compliance within the institution.	58(56.3%)	30(29.1%)	9(8.7%)	6(5.8%)	4.2	.57
Employees receive adequate training on regulatory requirements and their implications.	50(48.5%)	40(38.8%)	7(6.8%)	6(5.8%)	3.0	.56
The institution's management actively supports regulatory compliance initiatives.	57(55.3%)	29(28.2%)	10(9.7%)	7(6.8%)	3.5	.56
The institution has a dedicated compliance team for overseeing adherence to regulatory standards.	42(40.8%)	25(24.3%)	6(5.8%)	30(29.1%)	4.4	.46
The institution communicates regulatory obligations clearly to its customers.	48(46.6%)	22(21.4%)	15(14.6%)	18(17.5%)	4.7	.55
There is a clear process for reporting and addressing regulatory violations within the institution.	43(41.7%)	30(29.1%)	11(10.7%)	19(18.4%)	3.9	.46
The institution's regulatory environment meets both national and international compliance standards.	33(32%)	35(33.9%)	17(16.5%)	18(17.5%)	4.3	.57
Grand mean					3.9	

The results reveals that financial institutions has regulatory framework that is strong for the protection of customer data with updates of policy to comply with regulations Mean = 4.7, SD = 0.50) and concise communication to customers regulatory obligations (Mean = 4.7, SD = 0.55). There is monitoring of compliance efforts across departments (Mean = 4.3, SD = 0.47), and adequate resources are allocated for making sure regulatory compliance (Mean = 4.2, SD = 0.57). This notwithstanding, inasmuch as regulatory guidelines are communicated to workers (Mean = 3.5, SD = 0.56) and support of management for compliance initiatives (Mean = 3.5, SD = 0.56), workers training on regulatory needs (Mean = 3.0, SD = 0.56) need to be worked on. Added to the above, having a compliance team that is dedicated (Mean = 4.4, SD = 0.46) further, enhances adherence, but the violation of the process of reporting (Mean = 3.9, SD = 0.46) needs improvement.

Table V: Correlation between data protection and data compliance

Correlations			
		Data compliance	Data protection
Data compliance	Pearson Correlation	--	
	N	103	
Data protection	Pearson Correlation	.669**	--
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	
	N	103	103

The correlation analysis shows that there is a statistically significant relationship between data protection and compliance in Nigerian financial institutions. The P value is 0.000 which is ($p < 0.01$) indicating correlation against the threshold. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table VI: Correlation between privacy implementation and data compliance

Correlations			
		Data compliance	Privacy compliance
Data compliance	Pearson Correlation	1	.891**
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.000
	N	103	103
Privacy compliance	Pearson Correlation	.891**	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	
	N	103	103

The correlation analysis shows that there is significant relationship between privacy compliance and data compliance. The P value is 0.000 which is ($p < 0.01$) indicating correlation against the threshold. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Table VII: Correlation between regulatory environment and data compliance

Correlations			
		Data compliance	Regulatory environment
Data compliance	Pearson Correlation	1	.892**
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.000
	N	103	103
Regulatory environment	Pearson Correlation	.892**	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	
	N	103	103

The correlation analysis shows that there is a significant relationship between the regulatory environment and data compliance in the Nigerian financial institutions, with a coefficient of 0.892. The P value is 0.000, which is ($p < 0.01$), indicating correlation against the threshold. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result showed that the efforts of compliance among financial institutions in Nigeria are high with the cumulative mean of 3.7. Further, the study revealed that financial institutions in Nigeria showed good compliance with standards for data protection with an overall mean of 3.9. Also, privacy protection is effective among Nigerian financial institution with cumulative mean of 4.1 as well existing regulatory environment is effective with cumulative mean of 3.9. In terms of the hypotheses, the result showed a correlation between the three variables of data protection and data compliance, privacy compliance and data compliance and regulatory environment and data compliance.

The result of existing regulatory environment is effective with cumulative mean of 3.9 implies its effectiveness. The findings agreed with past studies that explored regulatory framework in different sectors, specifically in making sure of compliance, standards maintenance and efficiency promotion. Adeyemi and Olawale (2020) conducted a study on the effectiveness of regulatory framework in financial sector in Nigeria and the result indicated strong regulatory policies which aid the performance and accountability of the organisation. In the same vein, Okoro and Amadi (2020) conducted a study on compliance in the banking sector and found that effective regulatory environment enhance better compliance to safety standards and minimizes the risks and promotion consumer protection. The consistency between the results implies that regulatory frameworks, when well implemented, enhance efficiency and stability across diverse sectors.

Further, the results as well agreed with the study of Musa and Abubakar (2022) studies privacy practices in the banking sector in Nigeria. The result of the study showed a lack of privacy policies and compliance was strictly based on regulatory inspections but not based on the commitment of the institution to privacy

protection. The findings revealed that regulatory framework that is well structured help to promote transparency, reduces corruption and aid trust in the institution.

The cumulative mean of 3.9 revealed indicated the effectiveness of regulatory framework in the studied institutions, emphasizing that regulatory policies play an important role in operational efficiency and governance. This notwithstanding, in as much as there is high effectiveness, other researches like that of Nwankwo and Eze (2023) stated that the effectiveness of regulatory framework is often rely on the mechanisms of enforcement, cooperation of stakeholder, and frequent reviews of policy to address challenges.

The result further collaborates with global researches like that of Onu and Chukwu (2021) , who examined regulatory effectiveness of developed economies. The findings revealed that the success of regulatory framework is most at times depended on policies that are well outlined, robust enforcement, and the independence of the institution. The findings comparability implies that while in as much as there is effectiveness of regulatory environment in the research, constant monitoring as well as improvement are needed to maintain and enhance its impact.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated data protection and privacy implementation in financial institutions in Nigeria and the findings showed that efforts of compliance are high among the studied financial institutions in Nigeria; also, they showed high compliance with standards of data protection. Further, privacy protection and regulatory environment were effective among financial institutions. Also, there was a positive correlation between data protection and compliance, privacy and data compliance, regulatory and data compliance among financial institutions in Nigeria. The study concluded that the financial institution studied adheres to data protection and privacy compliance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study the study, the following recommendations are made

1. Financial institutions in Nigeria should put in place dedicated compliance tem that could carry out periodic internal audits to monitor compliance to policies of data protection.
2. Financial institutions in Nigeria should make sure of using international best practices, like ISO 27701 as well as GDPR guidelines to maintain world competitiveness.
3. Financial institutions in Nigeria should constantly keep up to data their privacy policies to align with evolving cyber security threats and advancements in technology.
4. There should be introduction of incentive by regulators for complete compliance like public recognition or tax benefits to encourage continued compliance. Further, cyber security resilience assessments should be compulsory and the periodic reports should be submitted to regulatory bodies.

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